

Digitalization of Religion in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges for Interreligious Dialogue

Luka Markus Barau

Department of Christian Religious Studies, Kaduna State University, Kaduna

Abstract

One of the key features of the 21st century is digital. Vital institutions of our society including the economy (finance), communication, education, medicine and others have been digitalized. The religious institution is not left out in this postmodern revolution. The intense religiosity of Nigerians extends to the internet, the digitalized mass media and social media. Here we find religious materials like the scriptures, (Bible and Qu'ran), Sermons, worship sessions, religious programs, documentaries, religious counselling and others as videos, audio and literary materials. Adherents of all religions have unrestricted access to these materials thereby acquiring knowledge of each other's faith previously inaccessible. It is undoubtedly true that this has facilitated adherents, knowledge and appreciation of each other's' faith. However, it is also factual that some of these materials are fake and inflammatory as they emanate from unauthorized, incredible and aberrant sources. This compounds the difficulty of fruitful and constructive interreligious dialogue. Using critical, analytic and descriptive methods, this paper sets out to explore the implications of digitalization of religion on interreligious dialogue in Nigeria. In the light of the ambivalent impact explored, recommendation are made for a responsible and constructive digitalization of religion that can pave way for fruitful interreligious dialogue and more peaceful coexistent Nigeria.

Keywords: Digital, Digitalization of Religion, Prospects, Interreligious dialogue

Introduction

It was Heraclitus the ancient Greek philosopher who is credited with the idea that “the only constant in life is change” It is also noted from our experiences that “Some change is fixed like the shift of one season to another while other change is evolutionary and progressive, tossing new circumstances our way as time goes on.”¹ In a nutshell, the implication of these statements for us humans is that our life and everything in it is subject to transformation. It is obvious that our concern is not with fixed change like the shift of season or succession of day and night. Pertinent to our discussion is the evolutionary and progressive change. At a global scale, we may arguably say that the modern and postmodern era in human history experienced the most dramatic and exponential changes. But what is ‘modern’ or postmodern in question? For the fact that ‘modern’ signify wide range of historical period and cultural context, definition is required. Mitchel observes that “modern can mean all of post-medieval European history in the context of dividing history into three large epoch: Antiquity, medieval and modern.”² We hereby adopt his concept of modernity as “the Euro-American culture that arises out of the enlightenment (of the 17th century) and continues in some way even more specifically to the 1910-1960 period.”

Postmodernity in this context logically refers to the developments and period beyond this epoch to the present, the 21st century. It is particularly convenient to adopt this model because “the dynamism of modernity is such that it spreads out from its European base to encompass the globe. The western originating institutions of modernity are dynamic and globalizing”³ The features of modernity that served as catalyst to the dramatic change include industrialization and mechanization, rise of nation states and representative democracy, discovery and colonization of non-western world, urbanization, mass literacy, proliferation of mass media, secularization, rationalization and increasing role of science and technology.⁴ The post-modern era adds to the list though according to Giddens “it is a state or condition of being postmodern after or in reaction to that which is modern”⁵, Additional features from it include the cold war and the subsequent space and arms race, eventual collapse of the

soviet union and the subsequent global resurgence of religion, sexual revolutions including rise of feminist and gay movements, decolonization, rise of peace, equality and anti-globalization movements, globalization and digital. It must be admitted and appreciated that most prominent among these features and catalyst of change is the progress and role of science and technology. In the post-modern epoch this seems to have reached its peak in digital.

A cursory glance at our daily life today reveals the immense impact of digital and digitalization. A notable personality admits that “in recent years, Nigeria has witnessed an unprecedented surge in digitalization with mobile network access assuming pivotal role. The proactive investment in telecom infrastructure has paved the way for the widespread adoption of 4G technologies and the nation is stepping into the 5G era.” The digital transformation in Nigeria manifests itself in various facets of our life as a country. Digitalization has diversified our economy and as Pharaoh further noted “a strong Information and Communication Technology (ICT) ecosystem is essential for efficient modern economies, enhancing business operations, public services and job creation.”⁶

Other instances include remote work from home, mobile money, digital banking, e-commerce platforms, app stores, ride-hailing apps, online advertising, online payment services cloud computing and participative platforms etc.⁷ the communication sector has reached a new level with our entry to mobile broadband solution of 4G/5G routers or smartphone tethering. And with the evolution of social media and digital mass media, our world has truly become a global village. Educationally, application and the subsequent admission and registration are done online. As observed by “Online schooling breaks down geographical barriers providing online classes, online course materials and online testing.”⁸ These are just a few. Of course one should not expect a dominant force in Nigeria as religion to be left out of the trending digitalization.

Much of our various religions have been digitalized ranging from availability in the internet of the scriptures (*e.g. Bible and Qur'an*), sermons, worship sessions, religious history, religious counseling, religious moral and doctrinal teachings, apologetics, religions political views, spiritual admonitions etc. This has undoubtedly furnished adherents of all religions with knowledge and experiences previously unknown and led to greater appreciation and understanding of each other. However, this digitalization has its downside. Some of the religious blog, post and contents are the work of unauthorized and incredible impersonators driven by desire for fame, economic gain or mere dubious motive. The religion in question hereby suffer misrepresentation, misperception and misunderstanding in this way, a constructive interreligious dialogue is at stake at all levels. This paper hereby seeks to investigate the ambivalent impact of digitalization of religion in Nigeria and in the light of the new insight make recommendations for better religious digitalization to enhance productive interreligious dialogue.

Conceptual

Before we proceed, let us first have a clear understanding of some key related terms as they are applied here.

Digitization, Digitalization and Digital Transformation

The terms above are often used synonymously without clear understanding of their differences and similarities. This is why it is necessary to clear the air of confusion and indicate their contextual use in this paper. All the terms above have the English root word digit which is borrowed from the Latin *digitus* (meaning finger, toe, breath as a measure) but also for medieval Latin meaning the Arabic whole numbers 0 to 9. Digitization therefore derives from entry of analogue information into computer system using digits (0 and 1).

This is why Aryne asserts that “analogue information is encoded into zeros (0) and one (1s) that computers can process, store and transmit. The process of digitization is the backbone for data recording making it an important aspect of digitization as the process of converting physical object into digital form. An example of this would be document scanning where text from physical paper is converted into PDF or other digital format which are then stored in the computers”⁹ it is evident from this analysis that digitization is the elementary step towards

digitalization or digital transformation. Its aim is to encode information in computers by converting from analogue to digital form for eventual use in digital technology. Digitalization seems more advanced and the next logical step after digitization. “While digitization focuses on converting and recording data, digitalization is all about developing processes and changing workflows to improve manual systems; digitized data are utilized to enable or improve processes.”⁹

An example of digitalization in relation to digitization is when digitized data of customers from various sources are automatically (digitally) processed to generate new insight from their behaviors. The aim of digitalization is information processing or how digitized data can be used to improve workflows through automating existing process. Digital otherwise called digitalism means “the condition of living in a digital culture.”¹⁰ The different dimensions of this phenomenon manifest itself variously. One major aspect is “the nearly constant contact with other people through cell phones” and quick access to people through world wide web and communicating through weblogs and emails.”¹¹ Others include constant communication through the social media like Facebook, WhatsApp, twitter etc. The mass media including newspaper and magazines are digitized. Educationally, E-learning, mobile learning and blended learning are the trend. Learning aids like the encyclopedia are undermined by Wikipedia.

Digital transformation is a phrase related to digitization and digitalization and is the peak of the two. “In digital transformation, digital technology is incorporated into all areas of the business to fundamentally improve efficiency in workflow and create value customers: cultural organizational and operation changes are implemented through the integration of digital technology.” From our analysis above, it is noticeable that the two terms digitization and digitalization are technically different. However, both terms are applicable to religion in Nigeria. Therefore, we may speak of either digitization or digitalization of religion in Nigeria depending on the context of application.

Religion

Despite the fact that the meaning of religion may seem clear, yet a universally accepted definition is nonexistent. This is why it is used in widely different senses. In its simple and original Latin usage (*religio*), Cicero defined it as “the giving of proper honour, respect and reverence to the divine, by which he meant the gods” and Cicero adds that it is not superstition, an empty fear of them (the gods).”¹² We hereby adopt a bit more elaborate definition of religion as used in this paper; it is belief in God or gods together with the practical results of such a belief as expressed in worship, ritual, a particular view of the world and nature and destiny of man and the way someone ought to live his daily life.¹³ Following the path of Cicero, we further note and differentiate religion from some practices which undoubtedly have religious significance but are not religion. They include theology, ethics, sport, medical practice, education etc. To be more specific this paper concerns itself with the three predominant religions in Nigeria; Islam, Christianity and African Traditional Religion and the interreligious dialogue between them.

Interreligious Dialogue

At the international scene, there seems to have been scholarly search and consideration for the appropriate term more inclusive than interreligious dialogue. Proposals include interfaith dialogue, trans-belief and inter belief dialogue or relations. There seems to be greater consensus on the term interfaith dialogue defined as cooperative, constructive and positive interaction between people of different religious traditions (faith), and/or spiritual or humanistic beliefs at both the individual and institutional levels.¹⁴ Inter-faith dialogue clearly involves the atheist, humanist, secularist, East Asian religions and others. However, our concept of interreligious dialogue is limited to Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religions which believe in a supreme deity. It is therefore more fitting to stick to interreligious dialogue. The English word dialogue stems from the Greek *dialogos* meaning conversation. It is a combination of *dia* (through) and *logos* (speech, reason). Therefore, interreligious dialogue in our context “is that part of dialogue which concerns itself with two persons or groups of different religions. As

religiously committed persons or groups, they came together to dialogue for the purpose of enriching, deepening and broadening their own religious life through the mutual understanding of one another's convictions and witness."¹⁵

From this definition, it is obvious that interreligious dialogue goes far beyond its etymological meaning as conversation. With the emergence of urbanization in our modern life, our society has become more religiously and culturally pluralistic thereby creating greater possibilities of other forms of dialogue. "This variety of possibilities has traditionally been reduced to four. They are; discursive dialogue (theological exchange), human dialogue (dialogue of life), secular dialogue (dialogue of action) and dialogue of religious experience."¹⁶

Discursive Dialogue (theological exchange)

Is also called dialogue of specialist, as the name suggest, this dialogue involves experts or specialists of theologies of the different religions. Tanko observes that "this dialogue aims at deepening and enriching the various religious heritages of the partners in the dialogue. The partners seek mutual understanding through sincere discussions."¹⁷ The peculiarity of this dialogue lies in its features as formal, structured and intentional.

Dialogue of Life or Human Dialogue

Unlike the one above is informal, spontaneous and unstructured. It takes place in public places like schools, hospitals, market, sport facilities, motor park etc. Thus through this dialogue, consciously or unconsciously "people of different religious persuasions live and work together and enrich each other through the faithful practice of the values of their various religions without the necessity of formal discussion."

Secular Dialogue

Is also known as dialogue of social engagements, this type of dialogue is an avenue where adherents of different religions participate in a common project beneficial to all. "The dialogue of social engagements deals with human promotion and the integral liberation of human kind"¹⁸ Example of this include construction of bridge across a stream, organization of vigilante to promote local security, charity and settlement of refugees etc.

The Dialogue of Religious Experience

Puts aside religious doctrinal and devotional differences, members of different religious traditions meet to experience the mystical religious reality all believe to approach differently. Example of this in Nigeria is Muslims joining Christian relative or friends for a thanksgiving service or wedding in the Church. Salihu noted that "It is common among monks of different religions. The motto of this form of dialogue is "doctrine divides, experience unites"¹⁹ Hence the basis for interreligious dialogue in Nigeria. But it should be noted that this is different from syncretism.

Digitalization of Religion in Nigeria

What is addressed in this section is sometimes referred to as digital, cyber or e-religion. On this media platform, a variety of religious issues concerning all religions are provided. It is not a new religion but a new medium of disseminating its values and practices. As it was earlier clarified, both digitization and digitalization apply here. The paper adopts the view of Sharmila that by digitalization of religion we mean "given different contexts and performances of digital religion in current times, a review can be taken of how religious practice has been described, approached and changed in the last few decades using internet, online, cinema, audio video, instruments such as smart phones, tablets and television etc."²⁰ Prior modernity, in typical African traditional society, communication was mainly oral and includes dance, rituals, drama, storytelling, ballads, chanters, flute praise singers, meeting songs, popular theatre, drums on gongs. This is the means of communication used in shrines or religious gatherings. It is noted that this greatly enhances traditional community ties but has limitation of failing to cover long distance and large mass of people.²¹ With the advent of Islam and Christianity and

subsequent modernization, modern technological means of communication sets in. this paved way for digitalization of religion in Nigeria. Its evolution is in two phases; the audio-visual and the internet and social media era.

Audio-visual

This is the pre-internet era “prio to internet dominance, audio-visual media was, though still is a very important interpersonal communication medium to deliver or convey message or video message to masses and their digital storage and reproduction for repetition.”²² Digitalization of religion in this era obviously entails the use of modern means like cinema, radio, television, tape recorder, video cassettes, projector and public address systems to practice and disseminate religious values. Religious worship and programmes in radio and television were common place. Muslim and Christian programs were broadcast both at weekends and weekdays. connected to this are the various religious television and satellites channels of both Islam and Christianity.²³ Examples include love world, CBN, TBN, Lumen Christi, Hope Channel, Sunna TV, Islamic Channel etc. others include announcements and advertisements of religious programs in other non-religious radio and television channels. The movie industry is also not left out. Religious movies are acted to emphasis Christian, Islamic and African Traditional Religious values.

The Internet and Social Media

The advent of internet and social media makes possible the peak of digitalization. Digitalization of religion is most manifested here. “In global religion... digitization has opened up new spaces for the mediation of religious information. The internet for instance has enabled particular religious community to circulate and publicize their message. The proliferation of religious website, forums and blogs, e-books and DVDs of religious materials care to be known as e-religion”¹⁹ Of course the use of the internet is maximized with the advent of cell phones in advanced form as smartphones and other gadgets like laptops, desktops smart TV etc. In connection with worship, religious programs and social media online, Campbell observes that “social media is changing the face of religion as it has become an important way to connect and make your religious experience a 24/7 experience rather than rituals to be on the weekend.”²⁴ Social media like the Facebook, Tweeter, You Tube, WhatsApp and play store and others are open sources of variety of religious materials ranging from sermons, scriptures, religious documentaries, marriage or pastoral counseling etc. this and much more have made digitalization of religion in Nigeria a reality.

Prospects and Challenges of Digitalization of Religion for Interreligious Dialogue in Nigeria

The general benefits and challenges of digitalization to human kind are too vast and beyond the scope of this paper. We hereby focus on digitalization of religion and its prospect and challenges as it relates to interreligious dialogue in Nigeria as clarified earlier. The 21st century can arguably be said to be the era technology has turned the world to a global village (of course not the global village in Dubai). “Today the world has turned into a global village because the fast and effective communication and travel help us to send information across the world in seconds or travel from one end of the world to the other within hours. Man has conquered time and space.”²⁵ While it must be admitted that digital technology has reduced the seven continents of the world (Africa, Asia, Europe, North America, South America, Australia and Antarctica) to a global village socially, economically, educationally etc., what impact has it on interreligious dialogue at least locally in Nigeria? How does it enhance or impede constructive interreligious dialogue between adherents of African Traditional Religion (ATR), Islam and Christianity? On a positive note, it is globally recognized that “the world has come closer. This has helped us understand one another. Internet has helped us stay informed, enlightened, entertained and connected indeed technology has brought us closer. It has turned the world into a global village, a global virtual village in true sense.”

This is important as the centuries long misconstrued perception and prejudices religious adherents have of each other are cleared. Practices, beliefs and messages of Islam, Christianity and ATR are opened for all to see in digital media. In this way, air of suspicion, fear and hatred spread by the uniformed, rumour mongers and religious extremist are minimized in Nigeria. But the above is facilitated by unlimited access to information available in the internet. In the pre-internet age, most religious adherents were at the mercy of their clerics. They relied completely on the subjective or objective information from them about the other religion or what they could tediously read on their own. But now “gone are the days when obtaining relevant information requires substantial effort such as consult physical books or researching through newspaper and magazines.”²⁶ With just a few clicks on your personal computer or smartphone you can now find a variety of resources... for practically any topic imaginable.” Thus without physical presence at the place of worship or religious programs or ritual of the other, enriching information about the other is accessed and much is appreciated. Physical boundaries are hereby bypassed.

Furthermore, prior to the digital era, interreligious dialogue (particularly of the expert or specialist) had to be conducted physically, nowadays, with the aid of what Ayne calls digital solution “Digital communication solutions such as instant messaging and video conferencing, they promote convenience, reduced costs and accuracy” Such dialogue could now be conducted online between individuals through zoom video conference calls from different religions and parts of Nigeria. The social media in particular has served as a bridge between adherents of different religions. It is argued that “on one hand, the increased access to people, content and information that new social media provides can promote tolerance.”²⁷ Through the social media, dialogues of life and social engagement done at sporting facilities, market, offices, schools, villages etc. are further cemented through friendly and informative interactions on the respective social media platform. For example most of such associations that cut across the three religions in Nigeria have WhatsApp or telegram account through which they fraternize and stay updated. They include town’s union, cooperative societies, Alumni associations, sport clubs, PTA, lecturers, students, school, teachers, etc.

Also there abound stories of marriages of disparity of cult (different faiths), relationships and productive and genuine friendships between persons of different faith which emanated from social media. In this and many other ways, digitalization of religion has greatly enhanced the prospect of interreligious dialogue in Nigeria. Unfortunately, digitalization of religion in Nigeria has double-edged quality. It is not without its challenges against constructive and fruitful interreligious dialogue. The history of world religious reflect the challenging issue of orthodoxy and dissidence which has caused serious internecine rivalry, clash of doctrines, devotion, teachings and even internecine wars. These internal religious disagreements pose challenge even for comparative study of religions. The disagreements are transported to the digital media where no central authority or legitimizations are given priority. Thus adherents from the other religion are confused on which religious material to recognize. This discourages and undermines understanding and appreciation of the faith by the other.

Another big challenge is privatization and commercialization of religion, a common phenomenon in Nigeria. At the pre-internet era “the religious establishments apparently began to lose their central role and individual could decide what to believe. However, it does have a limitation because commercial privatization of media could affect originally intended truthful religious expressions... in private service, the objective is to reach the largest audience in order to obtain the greatest profit.”³¹ This means that some religious material in the digital media are deliberately distorted and are half-truth merely for economic gain. This is even made worse with the advent of the internet. Numerous religious websites, blogs, DVDs etc. are there merely for the economic gain but lack authority and credibility.

The more challenging issue is religious materials placed in the digital media by radical and extremist religious groups and individuals. They are often inflammatory, fake and insightful. “The world is experiencing heinous crimes related to religious terrorism due to wrong interpretation created by digitalized religion. Consequently, public discourse disappears and negative rumours spread easily such as distorted interpretation of religion. In the end the collapse of meaningful intergroup communication brings society fragmentation.”³¹.

Besides this, we must also note the display of cultural and secular values in digital media which are morally contrary to any of the religions but are done under its (religious) cover. The advent of the internet and social media applications like Titok and Facebook complicated this. Examples include nude videos, sacrilegious comedies, irreligious and immoral music videos conducted under the cover of certain religious attire. In a nutshell, the negativity of digitalization of religion is most expressed in the digital media manipulation of truth, ideas and reality. Ali opines that this vulnerability applies to all digitalization in general.

Conclusion

From our analysis and assessment of digitalization of religion in Nigeria above, it is obvious that digital technology is a powerful tool employed by the religions. It is also important to note that its impact on interreligious dialogue is ambivalent. In one hand, it must be admitted that it has brought much good to all religions and their relations with one another. Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion have the greatest interconnectivity, awareness and mutual appreciation of one another more than ever before. These religions are therefore presented with immense opportunities and potentials to be blessings to the nation. On the other hand, digitalization of religion like every powerful force or tool of social change is imperfect and as such bears potentials of disrupting peaceful coexistence in Nigeria. It is important also to note that the inventors of digital technology in all its ramifications envisaged and intended much good for world of mankind. Its use for good or bad motive to promote or demote interreligious dialogue is a question of morality which much of Nigerian religiosity is devoid of. And this is a paradox all genuine Nigerian religious adherents are called upon to address with authentic change of heart.

Recommendations

The digital technology is admittedly an imperfect tool. However, to maximize the positive impact of its use in relation to interreligious dialogue in Nigeria, the following recommendations are hereby made. The paper recommends the Federal Government of Nigeria to mitigate poverty. Let effective, realistic and systematic programme be designed and executed nationwide to improve the economy to upset poverty and alleviate plight of the poor. The reality is that dangerous situation breeds dangerous people like scammers, cyber fraudsters, religious extremist and the uneducated and ignorant. To the Federal Government of Nigeria, the study recommends a just and effective regulation and if necessary a prosecution of those guilty of religious incitement and propagation of inflammatory and fake news and information through the digital mass media. To the Nigeria Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), through its appropriate sub-committee to assist the Federal Government with whistle blowing and bringing to book those guilty of propagating religious incendiary, predatory and fake messages. To all Nigeria religious adherents, it should be borne in mind that not all religious materials in the digital media and social media are true and authentic. Caution should be the watchword.

Endnotes

¹M. J. Julius, “*Heraclitus of Ephesus*” (2010), accessed 22nd September, 2023. <https://www.worldhistory.org>.

²M. Ali, & G. Hassan, “*Why change is the only constant and how to Embrace it*” (2022), accessed 20th September, 2023. <https://psychocentral.com>.

³M.I.Richman, “*Definitions & Characteristics of Modernity*” (2023), accessed on 6th October, 2023. <https://www.dbu.edu.org>.

⁴C. Barker, *Cultural Studies: theory and Practice*. London: Sage Publications, (2003),188.

⁵A. Giddens, *The Consequences of Modernity*. (Cambridge: Polity Press, 1990), 5.

⁶F. Pharaon, “*Nigeria and a sustainable Digital Transformation*” in Vanguard 30th August, 2023.

⁷H.S Iman, “*Taxation of Digital Economy in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects*. Accessed on 5th September, 2023, <https://awpavillion.com>.

⁸M. Onyia, “*Digitization of Education in Nigeria: A path to Technological Advancement.*” accessed 10th October 2023. <https://open.library.okstate.edu>.

⁹L. M. Aryne, “Difference and similarities: Digitization, Digitalization and Digital Transformation.” accessed 2nd October 2023. <https://www.globalsgn.com>.

¹⁰N. Negroponte, *Being Digital*. (New York: Vintage Books, 1995), 225.

¹¹S. Franklin, “Control” in *MIT Press*. 3 Sept. (2015)

¹²S. B. Ferguson, D.F. Wright, & J.I. Packer, “Religion” in *New Dictionary of Theology* (Leicester: Intervarsity Press, 1988), 575.

¹³C.E. Longhurst, “Interreligious Dialogue & Interfaith Relations? Or Perhaps some other Term?” *Journal of Ecumenical Studies*, University of Pennsylvania Press Vol. 55 No. (2020), 1.

¹⁴H. Mehta, “Minnesota interfaith group changes its name to become more inclusive of Atheist” St. Paul Pioneer Press. 28. (2014),

¹⁵P.B. Tanko, (2014), *Principles of Ecumenical and Interreligious Dialogue*. (Kaduna: Sunjo A.J Global Links Ltd, 2014), 37.

¹⁶Ibid, 52.

¹⁷J. Salihu, *Interreligious Dialogue and the Sharia Question*. Kano: Jalayemi Group 24 (2005).

¹⁸D. Sharmila, “Digitization of Religion” in *International Journal of Religion and Culture for Peace and Harmony* Vol. 5 ISSN (2013),2250-3331

¹⁹Ibid, 52.

²⁰Amecea and Imbisa *Communication, Culture and Community* (Vol. 2) (Nairobi: Paulines Publications Africa. 1999), 107.

²¹Ibid, 124.

²²H. Campbell, “Digital Religion understanding religious practice” in *New Media World*. New York: Routledge., 2013.

²³Ibid, 44.

²⁴Ibid, 50.

²⁵Kdcampus, “Technology Has Made the World a Global Village” accessed 28 October, 2023 <http://kdcamplive.com>. (2022).

²⁶Ibid, 15.

²⁷DBTI, *Bridging Babel: New Social Media and Interreligious and intercultural understanding*. (Georgetown: Georgetown University Press, 2010), 16.